

AI Application in Foreign Language Literature: ChatGPT's Impact and Skill Enhancement

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Abstract

This study investigates the prospective of incorporating input hypothesis, output hypothesis, interaction hypothesis and metacognitive theory into the best practices of ChatGPT in foreign literature. The study used an online survey involving 146 Chinese internet users to examine opinions on the use of ChatGPT for foreign literature analysis and tasks. Specific skills enhanced by AI integration, such as critical thinking, nuanced comprehension, and advanced linguistic proficiency in foreign languages are discussed in the research. However, there were concerns about its ethical implications when used for literary purposes because it may lead to biases, wrong information and risks which include plagiarism. During the application of ChatGPT, it was emphasized that comprehensible input is crucial to ensure that AI provided content is both understandable and suitable to learners' current proficiency level. Moreover, learners are encouraged to actively utilize ChatGPT as feedback as well as correction tool. Furthermore, this research allowed learners to engage in live communication through using ChatGPT as a speaking partner thereby negotiating meaning and getting instant feedback to support interaction hypothesis (IH). Underpinned by metacognitive theory, instructing learners to reflect on their learning process with the help of ChatGPT involves identifying areas of difficulty and seeking specific assistance, for example, learners may ask about linguistic doubts from chat GTP or test their understanding about certain concepts or vocabulary using it. In order to effectively integrate these hypotheses with metacognitive theories, interactive chat GPTs were designed which required learners' involvement in comprehensible input generation of language, output meaningful interactions and reflection on learning process; reading or listening to foreign language content (input), responding or creating content (output), engaging in conversation (interaction) tasks are assessed for their comprehension and performance levels (metacognition).

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Keywords: *ChatGPT, Ethical Implications, Literature Analysis, Paper Writing, Reading with AI.*

Suggested citation: Chen, X., Gao, Y., Tang, W., Guan, J. & Ryoo, J. (2024). AI Application in Foreign Language Literature: ChatGPT's Impact and Skill Enhancement. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(2), 3-18. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(2).01

Introduction

The exploration, comprehension, and evaluation of literature, particularly in foreign languages, have historically been intertwined with an understanding of cultural nuances and linguistic subtleties (Kilag et al., 2023). While traditional pedagogical methods offer invaluable insights, they often face challenges in scalability, adaptability, and catering to individual learning paths (Murphy, 2017). In this context, the burgeoning capabilities of AI technologies, especially in foreign language literature analysis, present a compelling avenue for exploration. This research seeks to explore how Chinese internet users perceive the use of AI models like ChatGPT in literary tasks implemented mostly through writing in foreign languages. As AI increasingly influences various sectors, its role in literature and language teaching warrants in-depth exploration. The study combines theoretical frames with practical insights thereby making it unique as it tries to unpack the potential impact that AI tools such as ChatGPT can bring into play concerning foreign language literature teaching as well as analysis.

The primary objectives are twofold: firstly, to assess how AI tools, particularly ChatGPT, influence and potentially revolutionize teaching methodologies in foreign language literature; and secondly, to identify specific skills in foreign language literature analysis that are enhanced by ChatGPT along with the perceived benefits and challenges. These research questions aim at giving a holistic view of ChatGPT's roles within the domain of foreign language literature analysis; hence providing knowledge on both methodological innovations as well as skill enhancement. The study is positioned at the crossroads between technological advance and educational transformation involving online surveying for multiple perspectives. It therefore contributes to the wider debate about integrating AI into education generally speaking but especially when it comes down toward foreign language literature.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Literature Review

Ignatovitch's (2021) research on the LearningApps service in teaching Russian as a foreign language underlines how interactive platforms can change everything. Interactive platforms help to learn languages better through interaction and individualized learning techniques. Meanwhile, Rudnik (2023) examines Metaverse Studio application to demonstrate how Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) can be incorporated into language education to provide immersive and authentic learning experiences. He highlights its versatility and engagement while positioning AR

as a useful tool for modern language educators. Liu's (2023) systematic review on using VR in teaching Chinese as a foreign language reveals the current state of this technology in his insightful article. The article shows that VR brings an immersive environment which allows learners feel like they are really inside the context of study but also points out some difficulties and limitations related to language teaching with VR technology.

Additionally, the application of AI models such as ChatGPT in literary tasks has gained much attention recently. Some studies including those by Holovatenko (2022), Deng & Xie (2021) have shown enthusiasm about AI models being used for literary purposes especially when it comes to improving reading comprehension skills, analysis, and reviews of literature pieces. However, at the same time these researches indicate some ethical concerns like biases or risks such as plagiarism that might arise due to usage of AI technologies thereby calling for responsible use of artificial intelligence which involves cautionary behavior based on understanding consequences beforehand. Further exploring this theme, Rudnik (2023) investigates how AI could reshape literature instruction necessitating guidelines so as to maneuver through challenges related with integrating AI into language teaching/literature analyses. Thus it is clear why responsible usage of AI is needed because you need to strike a balance between taking advantage from its benefits while avoiding possible drawbacks associated with this tool.

Theoretical Framework

According to Krashen's Input Hypothesis, language learners acquire language most effectively when they are exposed to "comprehensible input" that is slightly beyond their current proficiency level (Lantolf et al., 2023). This means that it should be understandable for the learner. AI can adaptively provide content that is just challenging enough to promote learning without causing undue frustration by analyzing a learner's progress and performance (Sayed et al., 2023). At the same time, Wei Zhou's study gives valuable insights on how Krashen's theory can be practically applied to improve English writing skills among polytechnic students in China but has some drawbacks (Zhou, 2023). The research shows that slightly advanced but comprehensible input is effective; nevertheless, it may not cater for different learning styles and needs among technical education students.

According to Swain's proposed Output Hypothesis, the learners can find gaps in their knowledge base, test cognitive hypotheses and think meta linguistically with this process. Worldwide, the Output Hypothesis has significantly influenced research on second language learning and teaching (Gao, 2022). For example, it shifted emphasis from input to input-output research in foreign language teaching (Li et al., 2023). According to this hypothesis, what matters most in language acquisition is output as opposed to input being more than output (Sun, 2022). Theoretically, claims of this hypothesis have been widely investigated with studies looking into its implications for language teaching practice (De, 2020). These investigations provide a basis for further research as well as improving practice in teaching languages (Wu and Peng, 2019).

Furthermore, there are a number of papers that talk about interactive hypothesis generation. For instance, Sohrabi et al. (2020) introduce LTS++, which is an interactive development environment for planning-based hypothesis generation in applications with unreliable observations. According to Yurieva (2019), the hypothesis under consideration here is aimed at understanding ontogenetic cognitive discursive mechanisms involved in narration through experimental research on the interactive

component in the oral narratives of preschool children. Also, according to Ferree et al. (2019), social cognition requires causal relations between the brain and its social environment which leads to their proposal of the interactive brain hypothesis (IBH). Finally, De et al. (2016) provides web-based interactive comparison of hypothesis tests used in statistical model checking so as to give users more insight into their characteristics”. These papers should be considered by anyone who needs an interactive approach while generating hypotheses or learning in different cognitive and social processes.

Importantly, integrating Input, Output, and Interactive Hypotheses alongside Metacognitive Theories into the optimal utilization of ChatGPT for foreign language literature is a highly encouraging strategy. Metacognition refers to the consciousness and control of one’s learning process, including planning, monitoring and evaluating comprehension and performance. It means being able to watch over and control mental processes so as to decide on your own level of subjective confidence by assessing how well lower-level operations are being executed (Lund et al., 2023). Intricate decision-making scenarios call for metacognition since individuals build up self-performance estimates (SPEs) from metacognitive evaluations (Lu et al., 2023). This is because it has social functions that contribute to collective judgment and coordination in group interactions (Fischer et al., 2023). Metacognitive monitoring is an educational procedure used for improving students’ learning abilities such that individuals gain knowledge through small steps of progressions (Wang, 2023). Different measures have been developed for assessing metacognitive regulation which include verbal protocols, questionnaires, metacognitive judgments; all which focus on different metacognitive skills while also evaluating diverse learning outcomes (Zepeda and Nokes-Malach, 2023). In order to get students engaged with comprehensible input, produce output in the target language, interact with relevant discourse and reflect on how they learn, this paper also aims at metacognitive theories into designing ChatGPT activities, including tasks which require students to read or listen to materials in a second language (input), to respond or to create their own texts (output), to take part in conversations (interaction) and then to assess both their understanding of the texts and performance (metacognition).

Methodology

This research uses the mixed research methods including library based research as well as the online survey aiming to gather insights into the experiences and perceptions of online users in China regarding their use of AI models like ChatGPT for tasks related to literature reading, analysis, and review based on the research questions. In this research, two areas are investigated. Firstly, the influence and potential revolution of AI tools in methodologies are explored by examining usage and effectiveness as well as ethical concerns and transparency. Secondly, specific skills enhanced with perceived benefits/challenges are investigated by discussing effectiveness and skill development, perceived benefits and challenges and ethical/practical concerns.

Table 1. Participant Background

Demographic Information	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	47	32.19%
	Female	99	67.81%
Age (years old)	20~29years old	53	36.3%

	30~39years old	79	54.11%
	40~49years old	11	7.53%
	50years old and above	3	2.05%

There are total 146 valid responses collected through the online survey conducted by Wenjuanxing (Wechat app) in China (see Figure 1). Based on Gender, there are 47 males (32.19%) and 99 females (67.81%). According Age (years old), there are 53 individuals aged 20-29 years (36.3%), 79 individuals aged 30-39 years (54.11%), 11 individuals aged 40-49 years (7.53%), and 3 individuals aged 50 years and above (2.05%).

Survey Analysis: The Influence and Potential Revolution of AI

The following investigation emphasizes the influence and potential revolution of AI tools by examining usage and effectiveness, advantages and user experience, as well as ethical concerns and transparency.

Figure 1. AI Use for Interpreting Literature

Figure 2. AI Effectiveness

From the perspective of whether the participants use AI tools for tasks related to interpreting literature, 44 (30.14%) chose 'Yes, regularly', and 102 (69.86%) chose 'Yes, occasionally'. From the assessment of the effectiveness of AI tools in performing tasks

related to literature, 44 (30.14%) chose 'Very effective', 97 (66.44%) chose 'Moderately effective', 4 (2.74%) chose 'Average', and 1 (0.68%) chose 'Moderately ineffective'.

Table 2. Rating Experience with AI

	Very poor	Poor	Neutral	Good	Excellent	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	0	1	29	95	21	3.93	0.61
Percentage	0	0.68%	19.86%	65.07%	14.38%		

While rating experiences of using ChatGPT or similar AI for literature-related tasks, there are 0 individuals (0%) who chose 'Very poor,' 1 person (0.68%) who chose 'Poor,' 29 people (19.86%) who chose 'Neutral,' 95 people (65.07%) who chose 'Good,' and 21 people (14.38%) who chose 'Excellent.' The mean value is 3.93 ± 0.61 .

Table 3. AI Usefulness

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean	Standard deviation
Frequency	0	3	25	82	36	4.03	0.71
Percentage	0	2.05%	17.12%	56.16%	24.66%		

Inquiring whether to agree with 'ChatGPT is a useful tool for literature reading, analysis and review', there are 0 individuals (0%) who chose 'Strongly disagree,' 3 people (2.05%) who chose 'Disagree,' 25 people (17.12%) who chose 'Neutral,' 82 people (56.16%) who chose 'Agree,' and 36 people (24.66%) who chose 'Strongly agree.' The mean value is 4.03 ± 0.71 .

An initial reliability analysis was conducted and are scored accordingly, consisting of scale items primarily addressing whether the participants are concerned about issues such as Intellectual property infringement, Plagiarism or incorrect authorship, Misinterpretation of the original text, and others (Table 4, Table 5 in Appendix). The results indicate that the Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC) values for all four items were above 0.50. Moreover, after removal, Cronbach's α for each item was lower than the total Cronbach's α , which was higher than 0.70. This demonstrates that these four items in Figure 6-2 exhibit good internal consistency.

Correlation analysis was conducted on Experience, Usefulness and Ethical Concerns (Intellectual property infringement, Plagiarism or incorrect authorship, Misinterpretation of the original text, Other), and their overall mean scores for Ethical Concerns (see Table 6 - Appendix). The results indicate: (1) Experience shows a positive correlation with Usefulness, with a correlation coefficient of 0.455, $p < 0.05$. However, its correlation with Ethical Concerns and its subtopics (Intellectual property infringement, Plagiarism or incorrect authorship, Misinterpretation of the original text, and Other) is not significant, $p > 0.05$. (2) Usefulness exhibits a negative correlation with Ethical Concerns, with correlation coefficients ranging between -0.286 and -0.181. Hence, it can be inferred that as Usefulness increases, ethical concerns regarding the use of artificial intelligence for analyzing literature tend to decrease.

Table 7. Regression of AI Usefulness and Experience on Ethical Concerns

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	P-value	R2	F
	B	SE	Beta				
(Constant)	4.48	0.55		8.15	0.00	0.09	6.67**
Experience	0.10	0.14	0.07	0.73	0.47		
Usefulness	-0.42	0.12	-0.32	-3.52	0.00		

Using Experience and AI Usefulness as independent variables and ethical concerns as the dependent variable, a regression equation was established for regression analysis (see Table 7). The results indicate an R-squared value of 0.09 and an F-value of 6.67, suggesting a good model fit. Specifically, the effect of Experience on ethical concerns is not significant (B=0.10, $p>0.05$). However, the effect of Usefulness on ethical concerns is significant and negative (B=-0.42, $p<0.05$), indicating that as Usefulness increases, ethical concerns tend to decrease.

Table 8. Ethical Concerns with AI Usage Frequencies in Literature Analysis

	Number of cases	Mean	Standard deviation	T	P-value
Yes, frequent usage	44	2.81	1.13	3.16	0.00
Yes, occasional usage	102	3.33	0.81		

Using an independent two-sample T-test to compare the ethical concerns associated with different frequencies of artificial intelligence usage in literature analysis, the results indicate that frequent usage is associated with lower ethical concerns, whereas occasional usage is linked to higher ethical concerns, with a T-value of 3.16, $P < 0.05$, signifying a significant difference.

Table 9. Guidelines for Using AI

Question	Grouping	Frequency	Percentage
Guidelines for using AI	Yes, definitely	38	26.03%
	Maybe	86	58.9%
	Neutral	21	14.38%
	Possibly not	1	0.68%

Table 10. The Use of AI tools and the Level of Guideline Requirement

		Guidelines requirement				X2
		Yes, definitely	Possibly	Neutral	Possibly not	
Use of AI tools or not	Yes, frequently used	20(45.45%)	20(45.45%)	4(9.09%)	0(0%)	12.73* *
	Yes, occasionally used	18(17.65%)	66(64.71%)	17(16.67%)	1(0.98%)	

While inquiring whether there should be guidelines for the responsible use of AI, 38 (26.03%) chose 'Yes, definitely', 86 (58.9%) chose 'Maybe', 21 (14.38%) chose 'Neutral', and 1 (0.68%) chose 'Possibly not' (see Table 9). Using chi-square analysis

to examine the relationship between the use of AI tools and the level of guideline requirement indicates that among those who selected 'Yes, frequently used,' the count of 'Yes, definitely' is higher than those who selected 'Yes, occasionally used' (Table 10). With a chi-square value of 12.73, it suggests that individuals with higher usage frequency have a greater demand for guidelines.

Table 11. The Effectiveness Evaluation of AI Usage and the Level of Guideline Requirement

		Guidelines requirement				X2
		Yes, definitely	Possibly	Neutral	Possibly not	
Degree of effectiveness	Very effective	22(50%)	20(45.45%)	2(4.55%)	0(0%)	21.73 *
	Fairly effective	16(16.49%)	62(63.92%)	18(18.56%)	1(1.03%)	
	Moderate	0(0%)	3(75%)	1(25%)	0(0%)	
	Fairly ineffective	0(0%)	1(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	

Chi-square analysis to examine the relationship between the effectiveness evaluation of usage and the level of guideline requirement reveals that individuals who selected 'Very effective' have a higher frequency in choosing 'Yes, definitely,' surpassing those who selected 'Fairly effective,' 'Moderate,' and 'Fairly ineffective.' With a chi-square value of 21.73, it indicates that those who perceive the usage as highly effective have a greater demand for guidelines.

Table 12. Involvement of AI Application Courses

Question	Grouping	Frequency	Percentage
Have the participants enrolled in academic courses related to the application of AI tools	Yes, online courses.	79	54.11%
	Yes, offline courses.	14	9.59%
	Not enrolled in any course	53	36.3%

From the perspective of participants enrolled in academic courses related to the application of AI tools, 79 (54.11%) chose 'Yes, online courses', 14 (9.59%) chose 'Yes, offline courses', and 53 (36.3%) chose 'Not enrolled in any course'.

Assessing the AI tools' effectiveness, user experience, ethical concerns, and transparency is crucial in educational environments. AI, particularly ChatGPT can has a chance to make massive change in revolutionizing the way people teach or learn foreign language literature and possibly improve the students' specific skills significantly informed by the the Input, Output, Hypotheses and Metacognitive theories.

Potential Roles of ChatGPT in Teaching and Analyzing Literature

AI tools, ChatGPT in particular, can help enhance interactive learning in foreign-language-literature-based language teaching or learning. Such technologies can increase the students' participation in learning and help them deepen their understanding of the literature content as well. This echoes with research done by Yang et al. (2023), emphasizing the importance of AI tools in foreign language education.

Potential Roles of ChatGPT in Teaching and Learning

The Interactive Hypothesis suggests that interaction, especially that involving meaning negotiation, could contribute to the students' language acquisition (Masrizal, 2014). AI tools like ChatGPT facilitate this through simulated conversations, and let learners practice real-time communication in a foreign language while negotiating meanings and getting instant feedback. When chatting with ChatGPT, the students can discuss the themes, roles and scenarios in the literature with it, which can intrigue their interests in reading the literature and get to know better the cultural background of the story as well. This approach which focuses on a pragmatic dimension based on speaking and writing skills would be revolutionary, particularly within literature studies where nuances and context matter most.

Additionally, AI tools, ChatGPT in particular, help create a balanced environment in terms of input and output in foreign language education. Such a balance is important in the context of foreign language literature teaching and learning. It facilitates the students' understanding of the text and their ability to express in a foreign language. ChatGPT could offer sufficient comprehensible input while simultaneously encouraging the students to adjust and improve their language output, both of which are crucial to language learning. For instance, it can produce challenging yet understandable text/questions that facilitate language acquisition. This is consistent with traditional teaching methods but also has the potential to transform them by providing individualized content instead of the one-size-fits-all approach common in language education. According to Merrill Swain's Output Hypothesis, writing (output) is just as necessary for successful language learning as reading/listening (input) (Bozorgian, 2012; Tsang, 2023). ChatGPT can assist learners in generating output like essays or summaries written in target languages and then give responses concerning these outputs. In this process, the students are not only recipients but producers of language, thus enriching classical literary analyses as well as composition activities.

Lastly, the use of AI based tools, particularly ChatGPT, provides support minority language learning and meet diverse language needs of the students. For example, if a student is learning a less commonly taught language such as Swahili, ChatGPT could help him/her explore literature related to this language. This approach aligns with the goals of foreign literature education which aims to equip the students with the needed skills, attitudes, and opportunities for success in a diverse and complex world (Alam & Mohanty, 2023).

Specific skills in Foreign Language Literature Analysis that are Enhanced by ChatGPT

The use of AI based tools, ChatGPT in particular, plays a key role in developing the students' abilities of analyzing critically and comprehending thoroughly of the language texts. Those kinds of tools can offer the students rich and contextualized language inputs, which could facilitate a deeper understanding of the literature being studied. Especially when the students are dealing with foreign language literature, the deepened understanding is crucial because of the underlying cultural and contextual implications of the text. In this study, 146 Chinese internet users were surveyed, and the vast majority had already utilized AI tools such as ChatGPT for foreign language literary learning, such as reading for general ideas, analyzing for deeper understanding of the details, or criticizing for different perspectives to understand the literature texts. Among those, 102 respondents indicated they use these tools occasionally, while 44

reported frequent usage. This finding underscores the widespread adoption and practical value of ChatGPT in the context of foreign language literature education.

Moreover, the application of AI based tools, notably ChatGPT, in the students' learning fosters their critical thinking and creativity, a core skill for students to succeed in their studies and lives (Hitchcock, 2017). The interaction with those tools stimulates the students to analyze and interpret literary content independently, thus cultivating their critical thinking competences. These abilities are particularly vital in their academic research and literary analysis, because in such kind of activities, the students are expected to critically and innovatively interpret the texts. ChatGPT, along with its diverse perspectives and analyses, serves as a platform to stimulate the students' creative thinking, challenging prevailing viewpoints and enabling the formation of unique insights and interpretations.

Additionally, AI based tools, ChatGPT in particular, play a significant role in enhancing the students' intercultural communication competences. Those tools can expose the students to literary works from varied cultural backgrounds and aid them in understanding and respecting cultural diversity which is increasingly important in a globalized era. This is in line with Byram's model of intercultural communicative competence which emphasizing the importance of understanding and respecting multiculturalism (Thayyib et al., 2023). In an increasingly diverse world, such skills are essential for the holistic development of the students (Alam & Mohanty, 2023).

Furthermore, according to Metacognitive theories, self-directed learning would be encouraged in literature studies that integrate AI tools like ChatGPT. This marks a significant departure from the otherwise traditional teacher-centered approaches. These theories are concerned with being aware about how one learns and regulating own learning process (Çini & Järvelä, 2023). ChatGPT help the learners ponder over their learning process, identify areas where they find difficulty while seeking specific assistance from it. For example, the students can rely on it to test their overall perception regarding literary concepts or even practice and evaluate language fluency.

However, the integration of AI technologies, especially ChatGPT also raised the issue of ethical considerations in teaching and learning process such as academic integrity. In his study in 2023, Mhlanga explored the responsible and ethical use of ChatGPT towards lifelong learning and claimed that the use of AI technologies, ChatGPT in particular, in education requires respect for privacy, fairness and non-discrimination, transparency (Mhlanga, 2023). Similarly, Celik (2023) investigated the teachers' professional knowledge to ethically integrate AI based tools into education in an empirical study and believed that the teachers performed a key role in the application of AI based tools in education. Celik emphasized that as long as teachers had more knowledge about interacting with AI-based tools, they would have a better understanding of the pedagogical contributions and ethical application of AI. This is particular important in the field of foreign language literary context in which original thinking and interpretation are much more necessary (Dulun et al., 2023).

The application of ChatGPT in foreign language literature instruction and examination might greatly affect or probably revolutionize conventional methodologies. It provides room for more individualized, interactive and reflective learning hence fitting well with modern pedagogical approaches that advocate for learner autonomy, engagement and practical skills' use.

Conclusion

AI tools including ChatGPT appears to be one of the effective methods for enhancing language proficiency in foreign language literature teaching and learning based on the established language learning theories and strategies like Input Hypothesis, Output Hypothesis, Interactive Hypothesis and Metacognitive Theories. Survey responses obtained from 146 Chinese internet users has highlighted significant concerns about the ethical implications of AI use in literature. It is important to address issues such as potential biases, misinformation and risks of plagiarism because they pose great challenges on this matter. Therefore, these worries call for caution in applying AI in literature thus there should be careful reading of texts and consideration of cultural nuances. Besides pedagogical challenges like AI response adaptiveness to various learning styles there are also technological limitations on interpreting cultural differences faced by AI as well.

From these results it can be concluded that even though artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT have a lot of potential value towards foreign language literature education; nevertheless, their application must be cautiously managed. Further research should focus on developing more advanced AI tools which can adapt better to diverse learning styles and give more accurate interpretations of cultural nuances in literary works. Furthermore, exploration into ethical considerations surrounding the use of AI within education is necessary so as to ensure responsible and effective implementation of these technologies in language learning and literary analysis.

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Appendix

Table 4. Ethical Concerns by Percentage

		Very unconcerned	Moderately unconcerned	Neutral	Moderately concerned	Very concerned	Mean	Standard deviation
Intellectual property infringement	Frequency	5	35	31	58	17	3.32	1.07
	Percentage	3.42%	23.97%	21.23%	39.73%	11.64%		
Plagiarism or incorrect authorship	Frequency	19	22	34	44	27	3.26	1.29
	Percentage	13.01%	15.07%	23.29%	30.14%	18.49%		
Misinterpretation of the original text	Frequency	12	28	29	49	28	3.36	1.23
	Percentage	8.22%	19.18%	19.86%	33.56%	19.18%		
Other	Frequency	25	31	53	30	7	2.75	1.11
	Percentage	17.12%	21.23%	36.3%	20.55%	4.79%		

Table 5. Internal Consistency Reliability Analysis of Ethical Concerns

	Mean of items after deletion	Variance of items after deletion	Corrected item-total correlation(CITC)	Cronbach's Alpha after deletion	Total Cronbach's Alpha
Intellectual property infringement	9.37	8.81	0.69	0.75	0.82
Plagiarism or incorrect authorship	9.43	7.93	0.66	0.77	
Misinterpretation of the original text	9.33	8.42	0.63	0.78	
Other	9.95	9.11	0.60	0.79	

Table 6. Correlation Analysis Among Experience, Usefulness and Ethical Concerns

	Experience	Usefulness	Intellectual property infringement	Plagiarism or incorrect authorship	Misinterpretation of the original text	Other	Ethical concerns
Experience	1						
Usefulness	.455**	1					
Intellectual property infringement	-0.019	-.260**	1				

Plagiarism or incorrect authorship	-0.057	-.206*	.675**	1			
Misinterpretation of the original text	-0.096	-.181*	.500**	.521**	1		
Other	-0.077	-.286**	.521**	.446**	.548**	1	
Mean: Ethical Concerns	-0.078	-.286**	.826**	.830**	.802**	.769**	1

Note: ** indicates significant correlation at the 0.01 level; * indicates significant correlation at the 0.05 level

